

Criteria for Vertiport Location in the Context of Urban Air Mobility

Oscar Díaz Olariaga¹

Universidad Santo Tomás, Colombia

Urban Air Mobility is an emerging transport technology that involves the use of electric-propulsion aerial vehicles, capable of vertical take-off and landing, for the transport of passengers and cargo across urban and interurban routes. These aircraft will rely, as physical support for their operations, on a new (ground) infrastructure known as the vertiport. This thematic review formulates and analyzes a variety of criteria related to the development (location, configuration, and operation) of vertiports in the city, which will need to be considered by urban planners in their future planning and deployment in cities/regions once Urban Air Mobility is adopted and implemented. The criteria presented herein include, among others, location, design, regulations, safety, environmental impact, social acceptance, and equity.

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¹ Doctor Ingeniería Aeronáutica y Doctor en Ciencias Económicas y Empresariales. Contacto: oscardiazolariaga@usta.edu.co

1. INTRODUCTION

The accelerated urbanization of cities [1] is generating a significant increase in road traffic, leading to serious levels of congestion and accidents, while intensifying pollution and noise in large metropolises. This produces negative impacts on the health of inhabitants and, ultimately, deteriorates their quality of life [2–4].

To address this global situation, urban airspace emerges as a solution through the emerging technology known as Urban Air Mobility (UAM). UAM is an emerging transport mode primarily intended to serve urban and interurban destinations, using electric propulsion, vertical take-off and landing aircraft operating from new (and relatively small) infrastructures known as vertiports [5–8].

Urban-interurban aerial connections generated by UAM will offer a new solution for fast travel to complement existing modes of urban public transportation. In addition to commercial on-demand passenger services (air taxis) and logistical services (air cargo transport), UAM will contribute to public services such as emergency response, medical or health services, rescue operations, surveillance and control, humanitarian missions, etc. [2, 9–11].

However, the innovative solutions of UAM lie not only in its new aeronautical and communication technologies but also in the ecosystem they will create —namely, a significant network of ground infrastructures supporting aerial operations, the aforementioned vertiports [12] [13]. This more urban concept represents a true challenge for urban planners and managers because these infrastructures must be planned and developed in such a way that UAM, as a service, not only serves to improve urban mobility in the city/region (integrating with the rest of the transport modes) but also —and even more importantly— be beneficial both for inhabitants and for the city itself [14, 15].

Formulating solid planning for vertiport development —understood as the location, construction, and operation of these facilities— will contribute to the introduction and rapid development of UAM and to its consequent success. Therefore, it will be of great importance to understand/define those criteria or factors that will assist in the development of vertiports in cities. This research, therefore, proposes a set of criteria, segmented into various thematic lines (considered most relevant in the initial phase of the UAM system), to be taken into account in the future development of vertiports. The criteria suggested here should help urban planners and/or public managers in designing and planning UAM support infrastructure while benefiting the development of this emerging technology, the industry, and, of course, the communities.

2. METHOD

For this review, a typical methodology used in this type of research —known as systematic mapping— was employed. It is the process of identifying, categorizing, and analyzing the existing literature relevant to a particular research topic [16–20].

Systematic mapping studies are designed to provide an overview of a research area by classifying and counting contributions according to the categories of that classification. It involves searching the literature to identify which topics have been covered and where they have been published [21]. Although a systematic mapping study and a systematic literature review share some common elements (e.g., regarding the search and selection of studies), they differ in terms of objectives and, consequently, in their approach to data analysis. While systematic reviews aim to synthesize evidence, also considering its robustness, systematic mapping focuses primarily on structuring a research area [22].

A systematic mapping study allows evidence to be charted in a domain with a high level of granularity. This enables the identification of clusters of evidence and evidence gaps to guide future systematic reviews and identify areas for further primary studies [23].

Thus, the steps of the systematic mapping process carried out here are [24]: (a) definition of research questions (which define and establish the scope of the research); (b) execution of the search for articles (all articles/studies/reports from both scientific literature and grey literature); (c) definition of inclusion and exclusion criteria; (d) selection of articles according to inclusion and exclusion criteria (identification of relevant articles); (e) selection based on title, abstract, keywords, and full text (classification scheme); and (f) data extraction and mapping of studies (systematic map). Each step of the process has an outcome, and the outcome of the process is the systematic map.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Definition of UAM

Urban Air Mobility refers to an emerging aerial transportation system that will use aerial vehicles (manned and/or unmanned), powered by electric propulsion, capable of vertical take-off and landing (or eVTOL, electric Vertical Take-Off and Landing), for the transport of passengers or goods along urban and interurban routes [5, 9, 25, 26]. UAM focuses on short- and medium-distance transport (from 5 to 300 km), with a capacity of 2 to 6 passengers (plus the pilot), connecting destinations within large urban areas or between interurban and even regional destinations [27]. Aerial vehicles providing UAM services will operate in low-altitude airspace [28, 29]. Several services —both public and commercial (or business models)— are envisioned within UAM. Among the first commercial on-demand passenger transport services: the air taxi [30–32].

3.2 VTOL / eVTOL Aerial Vehicles

Vertical Take-Off and Landing aerial vehicles (commonly known by their acronym VTOL) will be used to provide UAM services [29] [33]. Although the first UAM services are expected in the medium term (between 5 and 7 years, depending on the country or region), the aeronautical industry has been working for several years on the development of aerial vehicles for UAM services, of the VTOL or electric-propulsion eVTOL types [34]. Currently, more than 50 prototypes (most electric-propulsion) are in development or testing phases, and several are already certified for commercialization, with capacity for 2 to 6 passengers, flight times ranging from 25 to 350 minutes, ranges (coverage) of up to 300 km, and cruise speeds from 60 to 250 km/hour [28].

Currently, eVTOL manufacturers are proposing, designing, and constructing various technical configurations to enable optimal fleet operations, specifically [35–38]: (a) wingless multirotor configurations, (b) lift-and-cruise configurations, and (c) tilt-rotor systems. First, multirotor configurations (i.e., multiple rotors with propellers) consist of a central fuselage with various rotors; these eVTOLs achieve lift through high-revolution rotating propellers, providing stability and flight safety. These aerial vehicles have short range and are primarily suited for urban deployment due to the lack of fixed wings, resulting in insufficient aerodynamic lift during cruise and higher energy consumption in horizontal flight segments.

Second, lift-and-cruise systems are hybrid systems combining VTOL characteristics and extended-range properties due to the presence of fixed wings (where propellers/rotors are mounted). With a cruise speed of 200–250 km/h, these configurations appear applicable to both urban and interurban transport services (between adjacent or nearby cities). Third, tilt-rotor configurations allow the vehicle to take off and land vertically; as the aircraft gains altitude and speed, the rotors tilt progressively forward until the propeller rotation plane becomes vertical.

In this mode, the wing provides lift and the rotor provides thrust. These vehicles apply to intraurban, interurban, and even regional services due to their relatively high cruise speed, greater passenger capacity, and longer range. Figure 1 presents several eVTOL vehicle models of the types described above.

Figure 1. eVTOL aerial vehicle typologies for UAM passenger services [37].

3.3 Characteristics of UAM Airspace Usage

The expected progressive increase in the number of aerial vehicles providing UAM services will require the design and implementation of an airspace and air traffic management model [39, 40]. Research on UAM airspace management includes scheduling take-offs and landings, seamless integration with traditional operations, continuous trajectory management, UAM network management, airspace traffic management, and integration with traditional approaches, among others [41, 42].

Two major initiatives in the United States and Europe, funded by NASA and the European Commission, are leading research on UAM implementation. The most advanced is the U.S. initiative, the Advanced Air Mobility (AAM) mission [43].

One of the main pillars of AAM is automation, directly affecting air traffic management. In Europe, the CORUS project [44] is also relevant for air traffic management, as it focuses on integrating autonomous devices into low-altitude airspace. Ultimately, current airspace management tools and systems used in civil aviation will not apply to future UAM aerial traffic.

Initial UAM operations —characterized by slow pace and low complexity— will be executed under the current regulatory framework; however, as the pace and complexity increase, available regulatory options will need to adapt. As operations grow in volume and complexity, the implementation of UAM corridors may become necessary, and even essential, from the operational standpoint for airspace users and/or Air Traffic Management service providers [25].

According to research and technical studies, general airspace could (or should) be divided into three segments to separate aerial operations among all expected users (airplanes —commercial and private— helicopters, manned VTOL aerial vehicles, drones, etc.), considering substantial variations in operation and performance among these aircraft types, as shown in Figure 2 [25] [45] [46]. Thus, above 6,500 feet (1,981 m) would be assigned to commercial airspace, where commercial aircraft (passenger and cargo) operate and are controlled by the ATM system (Air Traffic Management).

The segment between 1,650 and 6,500 feet (503 and 1,981 m) would be used by VTOL passenger transport vehicles (e.g., air taxi, air ambulance). The region for large logistical drones (for cargo transport) would extend from 1,100 to 1,650 feet (335 to 503 m).

Finally, the segment from 150 to 400 feet (46 to 122 m) would be reserved for small drones (recreational, surveillance, infrastructure inspection, disaster management support, etc.) [47]. A no-fly buffer zone between 400 and 500 feet (122 and 152 m) is expected to ensure safety separation between small drones and manned VTOL aerial vehicles.

Figure 2. Distribution of airspace among different system users: above 6,500 feet (1,981 m) for commercial aviation; between 1,650 and 6,500 feet (503 and 1,981 m) for VTOL passenger aerial vehicles; from 1,100 to 1,650 feet (335 and 503 m) for large logistical drones; between 150 and 400 feet (46 and 122 m) reserved for small drones; a no-fly buffer zone between 400 and 500 feet (122 and 152 m) is foreseen for safety [45]

3.4 Vertiport

Definition and concept. The European Union Aviation Safety Agency defines a vertiport as an area of land, water, or structure used or intended to be used for the landing, take-off, and movement of aircraft with VTOL capability [5]. The U.S. Federal Aviation Administration defines a vertiport as an area of land or a structure used or intended to be used for the landing and take-off of electric (eVTOL), hydrogen, and hybrid VTOL aircraft, which includes associated buildings and facilities [6].

The concept of vertiports within UAM networks was popularized by the Uber Elevate program [48], which offered a comprehensive study and analysis of requirements for vertiport construction as supporting infrastructure for UAM services. UAM will require a network of vertiports with different characteristics and operational scopes to meet future urban and interurban mobility needs. Vertiport infrastructure is expected not only to support aerial operations but also to: (a) provide additional passenger-related services (entertainment, shopping, etc.), (b) support administrative management of the infrastructure (staff, offices, etc.), and (c) provide support for aerial vehicles (parking, maintenance, monitoring, etc.) [49] (see Figure 3).

Since a vertiport requires different infrastructure components depending on its intended use, location, development, and construction, three types of vertiports are anticipated [50, 15, 12] 51]:

1. Vertihub: Large-scale vertiports located on the outskirts of metropolitan areas. Vertihubs must provide parking (long-stay), maintenance, and repair facilities for eVTOL aerial vehicles, as well as central control systems for their operations (e.g., energy supply systems for charging eVTOL batteries). Vertihubs will

serve as UAM stations for long interurban and/or regional routes, and thus, the eVTOL vehicles operating from them will be the largest.

2. Vertiport: Vertiports will be located in the heart of the city and can accommodate both cargo and passengers. They will serve as UAM stations for both urban (within the city) and short interurban routes (between adjacent or peripheral cities). Typically, several eVTOL vehicles will be able to land simultaneously, each equipped with fast charging and energy replenishment systems and basic safety measures. The landside, where passengers are processed, will have substantial space and possibly some commercial offerings.
3. Vertistop: Vertistops will be small (initially no more than 1,000 m²), consisting of only one or two landing pads. They will be used solely for picking up and dropping off passengers and cargo and will serve as connection points between vertiports and/or vertihubs. On the air side, no complex service for eVTOL vehicles is expected, and on the land side, passenger services will be minimal (access and exit only).

Figure 3. Proposed vertiport configuration. Legend: (A) VTOL aircraft take-off and landing (pad) area, (B) VTOL aircraft parking (gate) positions, (C) terminal area (passenger management) [52].

Basic components of a vertiport. Numerous studies have explored the requirements or conditions needed for vertiport development (location, design, construction, and operation) [53-57]. A vertiport has a limited number of components and will serve very small aircraft; therefore, it will not require as much space as an airport.

It is estimated that in the initial UAM era, a vertiport will require between 3,000 m² and 12,000 m², depending on the number of infrastructure levels (this includes both the land side (passenger processing) and the air side (aerial vehicle processing)). This area will likely grow as UAM demand increases [58]. In vertiports, the built area of the land side is expected to occupy between 20% and 40% of the total installation, with the air side comprising the remaining percentage.

The air side of a vertiport includes the following basic operational facilities [59, 60]: (a) platform area (known in English as pad or vertipad) consisting of: TLOF area (touchdown and lift-off), FATO area (final approach and take-off), and operational safety area; (b) boarding/disembarkation area (gate), where aircraft remain with engines off to ensure passenger safety during boarding/disembarking; and (c) taxiways for VTOL vehicle movement between the parking/boarding (gate) positions and the take-off/landing (pad) positions.

- Air-side topology of the vertiport. The topology of the air side (where aircraft are managed) refers to the layout of the three basic operational components: take-off/landing pads, parking positions for passenger boarding/disembarking (gates), and taxiways for VTOL vehicle movement. Initially, three configurations (design, construction, and operation) are anticipated: linear, pier, and satellite [7]. These are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Air-side topology of the vertiport. Legend: dashed lines over a yellow background identify the taxiways enabling movement of eVTOL vehicles between take-off/landing pads (circle with H) and passenger parking/boarding gates (blue circles). Green areas (belonging to the landside) indicate passenger waiting areas, adjacent to gates for boarding or exit [7]

- Network configuration of vertiports. As with stations (or connection points) in other transport modes, vertiports will be distributed throughout metropolitan areas, forming a network, which must be perfectly integrated with the rest of the city's transport modes (and nodes) and other related urban infrastructures [61]. For network configuration, several factors and criteria must be considered (which will be discussed later in this article), including anticipated demand (origin-destination connections), environmental impact (especially noise), and proximity/connectivity to other transport modes, since UAM will be part of an intermodal transport system in the city/region. Easy accessibility to ground transport modes for first- and last-mile travel will be essential [62] (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Vertiport network scenario in the context of UAM. Legend: Black triangles represent high-demand areas, connecting vertiports with existing modes of transport to facilitate quick and easy user access. The network configuration will generate origin-destination connections (responding to anticipated demand) [62]

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Context

In the mid-1990s, Cohen [63] addressed the specific problem of locating vertiports within a UAM network by examining both siting constraints and land availability requirements. It appears evident that the issue of land availability is a critical matter when constructing new infrastructure elements for VTOL aircraft maneuvering. However, not many studies take into account all of the criteria (in addition to land availability) that could influence the siting, design, construction, and future operation of vertiports, and which, ultimately, could affect the usefulness and effectiveness of the UAM service [64, 48, 65].

Accordingly, the following criteria —grouped by area of action— which this research considers will have a significant influence on the siting, design, construction, and future operation of vertiports, are presented. These may not constitute all the necessary criteria to consider and analyze once UAM operations begin and as they evolve in the future, but they can be regarded as an initial starting point and reference. The criteria (and their associated considerations and factors) presented are as follows: a) national regulations; b) local

(or municipal) regulations; c) existence of physical (height) obstacles; d) land use; e) environmental; f) urban airspace; g) demand; h) contingency; i) equity; and j) public utilities.

4.2 National Regulations

It is highly likely that the regulations currently established that govern (in almost every country) all development and management of a nation's aviation infrastructure will apply (after relevant adaptation) to UAM support infrastructure. Thus, these regulations will play a significant role in the siting, design, construction, and future operation of vertiports [56, 13].

For the general public to allow the development of UAM infrastructure in their communities, it will be necessary to gain their trust regarding operational safety and the low or negligible impact of infrastructure and support facilities. Providing assurances to the public that vertiports will be required to comply with local legislation and that the national civil aviation authority will have oversight and enforcement authority will likely be a key factor in achieving this trust and, therefore, fostering a positive public perception of UAM [66, 67].

Although a vertiport is already defined, classified, and standardized (initially in the United States and in the European Union), many other concepts associated with UAM remain to be standardized and regulated [5] [6]. To enable appropriate governance and harmonization (both at the national and local levels), UAM terminology must first be formally defined at the national level. Adoption will also enable standardized terminology to be used locally/municipally in the development of zoning criteria, building codes, land use ordinances, etc. [25].

4.3 Local / Municipal Regulations

This criterion encompasses all local (or municipal) ordinances, standards, and regulations. Currently, interactions between civil aviation and the community in cities generally occur at airports, in airport-adjacent areas, and at any other site directly related to this airport-community interaction [68]. The stakeholders, their roles and responsibilities, and the taxonomy used for these interactions are sufficiently common that communication typically occurs without impediments. UAM operations will clearly change this dynamic. Not only will interactions be much more frequent, but the UAM taxonomy will evolve [69, 70].

Most municipalities adopt certain national standards that then become local ordinances. When evaluating potential site selections for vertiport construction, compliance with national/municipal regulations plays a significant role in determining whether a site will be viable.

Currently, this is more challenging because many of the standards associated with vertiports are still under development (or in analysis/study phases). A possible operating criterion during the development of these standards is to analyze existing regulations governing airports and heliports that could provide the basis for future vertiport siting standards [71]. These regulations can provide valuable information for municipalities to consider when developing ordinances for UAM infrastructure.

National laws and local ordinances that are aligned with accepted international standards are likely to be more easily adopted and contribute to uniform national vertiport implementation. In developing local ordinances for vertiport site selection protocols or design and construction requirements, referencing a national or international standard rather than a unique local requirement could reduce entry barriers for vertiport developers and operators [72].

For municipalities that seek to adopt UAM, having ordinances that address UAM infrastructure zoning standards, along with conditional-use permitting processes that acknowledge that laws and standards are still evolving and will likely require multiple interdependent levels of approval, will greatly aid approval processes [73, 74].

4.4 Existence of Physical (Height) Obstacles

Physical obstacles, particularly tall buildings and/or installations —whether permanent or temporary— in the area surrounding a vertiport can affect the usable airspace available. Along with potential limitations from existing infrastructure, allowable land uses (current and future) in areas adjacent to vertiports must be carefully considered. Early coordination with the relevant aviation authority during vertiport siting planning is essential to understand these limitations to potential approach and departure procedures before constructing a vertiport. In civil aviation, the treatment of physical obstacles in airport environments is thoroughly standardized and controlled by national aviation authorities through what are known as aeronautical easements [71, 75–77]. Adapted versions of these standards will likely be developed and applied to vertiport site selection.

4.5 Land Use in the Surrounding Area

Land use policy and/or regulation in a city is a fundamental criterion when selecting potential vertiport locations and for the future design of vertiport operations [51]. This criterion includes considerations arising from vertiport ownership but within the local neighborhood. These considerations can affect site selection as well as vertiport design, construction, and operations, and may even influence them throughout their operational lifespan [78]. A vertiport can also impact the surrounding area and alter these considerations [10]. This criterion includes factors that can be divided into two categories: those affected by the characteristics of the surrounding area, and those that impact those same surrounding areas. As discussed below, these categories are not necessarily mutually exclusive.

When locating vertiports, proximity to certain existing infrastructure (all subject to land use regulation), such as schools, hospitals, parks, fire stations, transport hubs, or intermodal stations, etc., can condition vertiport development and operations [63, 11]. Understanding where UAM services are needed or desired is another main siting criterion. Potential vertiport locations may be selected based on their proximity to areas of high projected demand, such as central or high-employment-density zones, sports facilities, leisure/tourism areas, freight distribution centers, modal transport hubs, etc. However, many cities recognize the need to protect residential or similar areas [79, 80]. These are locations where communities are more likely to raise concerns about privacy, safety, noise, and visual pollution. To achieve a positive public perception of a particular vertiport location, planners must develop and provide the right mix of services while also protecting community preferences. Various mitigation measures to strike the right balance include limiting vertiport size and operating hours, and limiting the size of aircraft operating therein [81]. Access to the vertiport must also be addressed during planning. For ground traffic, entrances and exits to/from the vertiport must be designed to avoid vehicle congestion (long queues), and on the other hand, allow easy access for users arriving via other modes of public transport [59].

4.6 Environmental Criterion

Vertiport construction must consider both the environmental impacts to be generated and strategies and protocols to mitigate such impacts [82]. In most countries, there is a national environmental agency or authority and related legislation that such an agency enforces. Thus, in the (very soon) context of UAM, these agencies in different countries will have to evaluate the environmental effects of proposed actions before making decisions. Once a baseline for the affected environment is established, according to current national legislation, local jurisdiction must then assess whether additional studies need to be conducted to fully evaluate any environmental impacts that may occur as a result of vertiport siting and operation [83].

4.7 Urban Airspace

This criterion encompasses how management of the surrounding airspace impacts vertiport operations. The immediate airspace around a vertiport and how it is managed has a significant impact on operations

and must be considered when assessing vertiport siting. Several factors directly impact available airspace to support operations near the vertiport; these include proximity to airports, no-fly zones, special-use airspace, or sensitive flight areas [85]. These nearby urban airspace restrictions may limit the size and/or location of approach routes, departure corridors, or holding areas. Complying with these restrictions can reduce the total number of operations that the vertiport can support [39].

The projected density of operations in the airspace near a vertiport is also an important siting consideration. As operational density increases, so does the need for both tactical and strategic air traffic flow management. However, options to manage air traffic while aircraft are airborne may be limited, depending on several factors. For example, the relative size of available airspace surrounding the vertiport for urban operations may be insufficient for projected demand and may result in selecting an alternative vertiport site [60]. Ultimately, understanding and addressing urban airspace considerations will require close coordination with the national aviation authority.

4.8 Demand

Various studies propose (at the simulation level or as conceptual models) vertiport siting within cities (selected as case studies or potential application locations) in response to projected local demand behavior [64, 12, 86–89, 51, 90]. Accordingly, the following demand-related factors, expected to influence urban vertiport siting, are presented and analyzed:

- **Population Density.** Population as an influential factor for vertiport siting is commonly used in related research [91] [92] [93] [94]. In general, studies propose locating UAM vertiports near or within areas with significant population concentration, as these could represent a greater number of users. While UAM is not yet an available transport mode, there exists at least one important similarity with current public transport: stations (buses, metro, BRT, trains). For users to access UAM flights, they must first access a UAM station. As such, public transport station accessibility guidelines can serve as a proxy for UAM station accessibility. Although a large population does not necessarily equate to high UAM ridership, it remains an important element for a potential market.
- **Income Level (Purchasing Power).** When UAM service begins, its fares are expected to be high (or expensive relative to other transport modes) [48]. Therefore, current studies consider this factor (identifying zones with residents of high or very high purchasing power) when determining or modeling vertiport locations, as it will directly influence potential service demand [95, 64, 96].
- **Tourist Interest Zones.** Tourism within cities and surrounding areas generates demand for urban and interurban transport —i.e., tourism is a strong driver of travel [97]. Thus, the catchment area of any transport mode must cover tourism attractions. The way tourists reach these attractions must be convenient [98]. Studies estimate that the number of VTOL tourist trips (departing from vertiports) could capture between 5% and 20% of total travel demand generated by tourism in a city and/or its periphery [12, 99].
- **Major Transport Nodes.** Research anticipates potential demand for UAM services from and to major city transport hubs (airports, regional/suburban rail stations, long-distance train stations, long-distance bus terminals) [64] [48]. Major transport nodes are also important concerning intermodality. Providing UAM ground infrastructure at major transport nodes can enhance speed, flexibility, and travel convenience, as long-distance passengers can switch travel modes almost seamlessly. VTOL aircraft could serve as the first and last mile of a long-distance trip, where the airplane or long-distance train acts as the main carrier [48, 51].
- **High-Employment-Density Areas.** As with population, employment is a commonly used factor in related research [12, 95, 100]. Many cities or metropolitan regions worldwide have areas with high commercial, industrial, financial, or governmental activity, and therefore substantial concentrations of workers [86].

As a result, the existence of vertiports serving these high-employment-density areas could generate significant service demand.

4.9 Contingency

This criterion can be divided into three groups: contingencies involving the aircraft, contingencies involving the vertiport, and those related to procedures and preparedness for potential contingencies. Aircraft contingencies originate in the aircraft but affect vertiport design and operations. An immediate landing emergency could be mitigated by constructing sufficient emergency landing sites or by requiring at least one open pad at a multi-pad vertiport [39]. An onboard aircraft fire would be mitigated during vertiport design through installation of firefighting equipment, and further mitigations could include conducting drills to test fire response plans along with vertiport closure until the aircraft fire is extinguished [101].

Vertiport contingencies include power loss, hazardous material spills, fires, sensor signal loss, equipment failures, or weather-related events affecting operations. Because vertiports are likely to be more closely integrated within communities than traditional airports, risks associated with such integration and proximity to specific locations must be considered [13].

Contingencies to be considered during vertiport planning include distance and travel time to emergency services, availability and types of medical facilities, and the availability of alternative transport modes if the vertiport is forced to shut down. Identification of contingency considerations must be subject to a rigorous process during planning and design to improve vertiport operational safety and reduce the need for potentially costly retrofits to mitigate unconsidered contingencies [102].

4.10 Equity

Equity, in the context of UAM, means that all community residents have access to the same opportunities and that vertiport development considerations and outcomes bring reasonable benefits for all without unduly burdening any segment of the population. Adopting an inclusive approach throughout the planning and operation of UAM services is imperative to achieving equity. Maintaining ongoing dialogue with all segments of the potentially affected population can help ensure equity is achieved [103, 8, 104].

Equity considerations include primarily two types: social equity and access equity. Social equity considerations involve ensuring that people across all demographic socioeconomic groups benefit from UAM services [105, 82]. Access equity considerations involve ensuring that all community members can use this new transport mode and are a key part of UAM's definition [94]. These considerations highlight the desire to find ways to equitably allocate vertiport capacity and surrounding airspace, including appropriately prioritizing operations, such as giving precedence to emergency services.

4.11 Public Utilities

As the functional and operational needs of future UAM services become clearer, it is anticipated that future vertiports will also need to have typical utilities (electricity, gas, water, communications, etc.). Infrastructure and public utilities play a significant role in vertiport siting and construction considerations [72].

Zoning and land use designations also impact utilities. For example, a vertiport may require specific zoning to store fuel onsite, or a local land use plan prioritizing agricultural uses may prevent a vertiport from accessing appropriate electrical service.

The requirement for easements on private property to provide access to the electrical grid or other utilities is another aspect that is crucial to assess for a potential vertiport site [10]. The approval process for utility

access likely extends beyond simple physical considerations and includes community objectives, such as carbon neutrality goals or impacts on other community services.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study has presented and analyzed an extensive set of criteria and considerations that are expected to influence/affect/condition the siting, design, construction, and operation of a vertiport. The purpose of this study was to fill a gap in related literature and to provide a document that can serve as a starting point for urban planners, decision-makers, and public policymakers in cities/regions that choose to adopt and implement UAM services.

The criteria presented here aim to provide value to future stakeholders in the UAM ecosystem for various purposes. For example, these considerations may help potential vertiport operators assess business model trade-offs; support evaluation of vertiport siting or relocation based on demand behavior; assist in network design and development; configure the network of destinations offered by UAM services; help integrate UAM into existing public transport systems; contribute to strengthening certain commercial, business, and industrial activities within the city/region; and lastly, though not least, contribute to establishing a communication and interaction framework with communities to secure their acceptance of UAM development in their cities.

Ultimately, UAM is closer to becoming a reality than many urban planners and public administrators might believe. The rapid advancement of technologies related to UAM, along with the definition and approval of relevant regulatory frameworks, establishes a legitimate foundation for the imminent introduction of UAM services in cities. In many cases —perhaps most— this development is going unnoticed by local authorities. Consequently, it would be highly advisable for urban planners and any other relevant local/national public authorities or agencies to include emerging (and imminent) Urban Air Mobility in their agendas sooner rather than later.

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